

Horizon 2020
Programme

Sm@ll Ruminant Technologies

Cost/Benefit Analysis

Tool / Technology: Feed ration planner

Analysis prepared by (country): UK

Production type the tool/technology is relevant for: Dairy / Meat / **Both**

Description of the “benchmark” farm for which the analysis is performed:

Country: UK

Production type:

Mainly outdoors / Housed 0-3 months a year / Housed 4-8 months a year / Mainly indoors

Farm grazing area: ~1,000 ha

Species: **Sheep** / Goat

Number of animals: 700 ewes

Breed: Predominantly Scottish Blackface

Number of staff: 2

This project has received funding from
the European Union's Horizon 2020
research and innovation programme
under grant agreement N° 101000471.

Costs

Initial set-up

- **Capital costs (Large items e.g. a weigh crate, auto-drafter, etc.):**

€1 - €500 €501- €1,000 €1,001-€2,500 €2,501-€5,000 €5,001-€15,000 > €15,000

- **Individual costs (Smaller items e.g. per tag, per sample, per collar):**

€1 - €20 €21- €50 €51-€200 €201-€500 > €500

- **Equipment leasing costs (if not purchased):**

Annual Monthly Weekly €1 - €50 €51-€200 €201-€500 > €500

- **Lifetime of the technology (approximately how long will it last before needing replaced)?**

1 – 4 weeks 1-6 months 6 – 12 months 1-2 years 2-5 years > 5 years

- **Farm infrastructure requirements:** Decrease Increase No change

- **Percentage of animals within the flock/herd that use/are equipped/take advantage of the technology? 100 %**

Running costs

- **Power source requirements (tick all that apply):**

Not required Mains Battery Solar Other

- **Subscription fee – Needed? Yes / **No****

- **If yes**

Per flock / herd <input type="checkbox"/>	Per individual animal <input type="checkbox"/>	Per unit <input type="checkbox"/>
Annual <input type="checkbox"/>	Monthly <input type="checkbox"/>	Weekly <input type="checkbox"/>
€1 - €50 <input type="checkbox"/>	€51 - €200 <input type="checkbox"/>	€201 - €500 <input type="checkbox"/> Over €500 <input type="checkbox"/>

- **Additional licences or permits required? **No** Yes – Annual / Yes – Monthly / Yes - Weekly**

If yes, cost: €1 - €50 €51 - €200 €201 - €500 Over €500

- **Maintenance cost – included in the subscription? Yes / **No** / Not applicable**

If no, cost per month: €1 - €50 €51 - €200 €201 - €500 Over €500

- **Maintenance / replacement parts:**

Easy to obtain Difficult to obtain Not obtainable Don't know

- **Technical / mechanical support provided on farm, after purchase? Yes / **No****

Training requirements

- **Training required to install / use? **Yes** / No**

If yes, time range? Up to an hour Half day Full day More

- **Additional technical advice required (e.g. advisor time)? Yes / **No****

- **Are there additional costs associated with training and/or technical advice? Yes / **No****

Benefits (tick all that apply)

Management

- Labour / time saving.
- Accuracy of records (health, management, movements etc.).
- Management decisions for animal groupings.
- Better individual animal management.
- Improved medicine use.
- Better nutrition / meeting requirements better.
- Improved use of feed resource (grazing, concentrates, etc.).
- Product quality improvements (e.g. hay, carcass, growth, milk, etc.).
- Increased information on production system.
- Opportunity for sharing / moving device (more than one location).

Animal

- Reduced stress to the animal(s).
- Improved welfare of the animals(s).
- Additional information on animal behaviour.
- Information on water intake / water availability.
- Information on food intake / food availability.

Technical

- Compatibility with other devices.
- Ease of data transfer to other software.
- Easy to use once installed.

Other

- Reduced stress to farmer / staff .
- Environmental benefits (e.g. reduced wastage, improved biodiversity, etc.)
- Helps to attract new entrants in to the small ruminant industries.

Another benefit not listed? Please give details:

The tool is free to download from the AHDB webpage.

Data helps to plan when additional supplementation is required.

Overall summary:

- **Ease of use?** *Scale 1 (Complicated) – 10 (Simple)*

1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 **9** 10

- **Value for money (for this type of benchmark farm)?** Yes / ~~No~~ / ~~Maybe~~

- **Recommend this tool/technology for use on other types of farm?**

Yes / ~~No~~ / ~~Maybe~~

- **Additional comments?**

The tool is free but requires regular measurements using a plate meter/sward stick to collect pasture data.

Mainly useful for improved and/or semi-improved grazing. Might not be so practical for extensive hill ground grazing.

Data collected can be used with some mobile phone apps and farm management software (some of these may involve a subscription fee).

More sophisticated ration software are available, which come at a cost, but allow more detailed rations to be set-up for various different classes of animal (pregnant ewes, finishing lambs, etc.).

e.g. **DietCheck for Sheep** - <https://dietcheck.co.uk/software/dietcheck-for-sheep>.
 Small Ruminant Nutrition System - ([Model: SRNS \(nutritionmodels.com\)](http://Model:SRNS(nutritionmodels.com)))

